

5IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP5 Dissemination and education for HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public

D5.8 Report describing synthesis of evidence and testing the knowledge databank and recommendations for sustainability

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Document History

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Abstract

The aim of task 5.2 is to develop an EU centralised digital knowledge bank for healthcare professionals and pregnant or breastfeeding women with up to date information on drug use before and during pregnancy and breastfeeding, and on the risks of untreated disease (in English), by combining information from different sources and providing common knowledge. This report describes the synthesis of evidence and testing the knowledge databank and recommendations for sustainability.

During the process of writing the information pages, additional needs have been identified, mainly concerning efficiency of writing the pages. In addition, there was found to be a stronger desire than previously anticipated for the provision of translation of knowledge pages for countries that do not have a local knowledge bank. These updates are intended to ensure the knowledge bank is novel and adequately addresses the needs of women and healthcare professionals throughout Europe. We are currently working on these aspects.

Concerning the technical development of the MUMS website, the functionalities of the public website and those needed to upload an information page are realized. For these functionalities, the focus of the development team is on testing and fine tuning. In parallel they are working on the other predefined functionalities.

For sustainability steps have been set into drafting the operational and governance model, as well as the legal setting. The European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) has agreed to take over the governance and operation of MUMS after the ConcePTION project ends, to be hosted by one of its member centres. However, funding is required. Ideally MUMS should have a three-year funded plan, covering maintenance and incremental growth.

Introduction

The aim of task 5.2 is to develop an EU centralised digital knowledge bank for healthcare professionals and pregnant or breastfeeding women with up to date information on drug use before and during pregnancy and breastfeeding, and on the risks of untreated disease (in English), by combining information from different sources and providing common knowledge. The knowledge bank provides information for healthcare professionals and pregnant or breastfeeding women. Their needs and expectations have been explored during the landscape analysis (see Deliverable 5.4 Report with landscape analysis). In addition, the knowledge bank can be used by individual TIS centres to support their day to day work.

A description of the functionality of the knowledge bank and the standard operating procedure (SOP) for for evidence retrieval and synthesis for the knowledge bank have been described in Deliverables 5.1 and 5.3 respectively. The past two years the work focused on writing the information pages and redesigning this process. In parallel, the technical functionalities of the knowledge bank have been developed and tested. Also, a plan has been made for making the knowledge bank sustainable.

This document describes the current status of evidence retrieval, development of the knowledge bank and testing of the functionalities, and the plan for sustainability.

MUMS model update

Writing of information pages

During the writing process of the information pages, additional needs have been identified. While the previously proposed model was considered the 'gold-standard' approach to searching, reviewing, critically appraising, assimilating and summarising information about a medication in pregnancy, the proposed process was very labour intensive, did not utilise existing resources developed by contributing partners and did not capitalise on work-sharing opportunities.

In response a more efficient model for work sharing has been followed, where existing sources are leveraged to compile summary pages, which will then be reviewed by an editorial board. In this way we are able to create a knowledge bank with information about more drugs of interest, making the knowledge bank more suitable. It was identified that writing breastfeeding information pages takes relatively much time as experience in this field is lacking within the WP5.2 writing group. Additionally, as there are existing sources with reliable freely available information in English (eLactantia and LactMed[®]) about the use of medicines during breastfeeding, it has been decided to link to these sources instead of writing the pages ourselves.

Translation of information pages

As there is a stronger desire than previously anticipated for the provision of translation of knowledge pages for countries that do not have a local knowledge bank, we are currently piloting the option of translations in countries who do not having a local knowledge bank (with or without TIS centre). It is however challenging to reach patients in countries without TIS centre.

We are currently piloting two approaches to translation of KB content:

- (1) For countries who do not have a TIS – example Poland

This pilot model is intended to explore translation of KB content in countries without a TIS centre. We are engaging with external translation companies to translate the initial 30 information pages into a single language, namely Polish. In the absence of a local TIS centre or TIS representative in Poland, we are exploring how these translations can be verified by a healthcare professional in the local country/local language to ensure accuracy and quality. We are exploring connections within the ConcePTION network to link with a university in Poland to verify the translations.

(2) For countries who do have a TIS – Example Italy

Through ENTIS, we are engaging with colleagues in TIS centres in Italy to explore how ‘in-house’ translation of KB content can be carried out. Under this model, Italian TIS centres will translate the information pages into Italian and verify the accuracy and quality themselves. Additional funding will be required to fund TIS centre translations.

Development functional requirements

Public website (frond end)

Deliverable 5.1 described the functional requirements of the knowledge bank. All functional requirements for the home page are implemented technically. These include the functionalities for the search, recent knowledge updates, in focus, and maternal medical conditions. For the ‘search’ specifically, the development team is also looking at the performance and spelling errors.

All functional requirements for the information pages are implemented technically. After clicking on the title, the visitor will be directed to the knowledge page. Here the summary will be shown, the detailed information is only visibly completely if a used click on ‘read more’. On the right of the page, related information pages are shown and the visitor can directly read these pages by clicking on the title.

The development team is currently working on building the functionality to make it possible for users to subscribe to a RSS feed containing updates knowledge pages/news. In addition, the keywords of knowledge pages will be included as metatags in the code and the title of the knowledge page will be shown using a H1 tag on the website and will be part of the URL to increase the ranking on relevant keywords. For search engines like Google to be able to index the information pages, a custom sitemap will be developed.

WP5.2 Writing team (Back end)

Users of the back end login by username and password. All functionalities to upload an information page on the website have been developed. These include information pages overview, status, filter for translation option, last changes from/to (date), keywords for search functionalities, links to other information pages.

The development team is currently working on additional security for the back end login, the functionality to add internal comments, references, the search list (drugs, ATC and SNOMED), and a functionality to support the writing process by Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Planner, and Microsoft SharePoint.

Branding

The front of the home page is demonstrated below. The name of the ConcePTION knowledge bank is 'MUMS: Mothers Using Medicines Safely'. Preferences for the type of image in the logo and colors have been explored by using a poll. The logo has been developed in collaboration with the University of Stockholm (copy right agreed on).

At the bottom of the Home page acknowledgements and logos of participating parties for IMI are displayed. Before launching the website, WP5 will check with the IMI communication department if all participating parties are displayed correctly.

The ConcePTION project has received funding from the [Innovative Medicines Initiative](#) Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 821520. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's [Horizon 2020](#) research and innovation programme and [EFPIA](#). The development of the knowledge bank was conducted as part of the ConcePTION consortium. This content of the knowledge bank only reflects the personal views of the stated authors.

Other functions

Other functionalities are currently being progressed:

- Link to ConcePTION Glossary
- Development of an About Us section
- Inclusion of information pages for specific maternal medical conditions.

Plan for sustainability

During the ConcePTION project, MUMS has been developed on the basis of well researched user needs and requirements, as a fully implemented web portal, also suitable for mobile device access. After ConcePTION, it has illustrative content comprising around 30 medicines of high frequency use, developed through a formal and documented editorial and governance process.

The European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) has agreed to take over the governance and operation of MUMS after the ConcePTION project ends, to be hosted by one of its member centres. However, funding will be required to widen the medicines coverage, translate the lay summaries into multiple languages, to maintain and update the existing content and to promote the resource within target countries (to be agreed). The operational and governance model, as well as the legal setting, are being designed. The intended model is summarised below.

ENTIS:

- A committee of ENTIS will review and endorse the compiled summaries
- TIS members will be contracted by the coordinating centre for participating in the compiling process of the summaries (MUMS team)

ENTIS will nominate a TIS centre as coordinating centre. This centre will be responsible for:

- Hosting MUMS knowledge bank, coordinate IT updates, management and maintenance
- Managing compilation and updates of summaries
- Coordination of endorsement ENTIS committee review of completed summaries
- Managing translations of summaries and updates
- Manage local endorsement of translations by TIS or local resources in countries without TIS

A sponsorship model is being pursued, through charitable agencies, so that the resource can always be free to access by the public and healthcare professionals. Industry sponsorship is deliberately not being pursued in order for MUMS to be demonstrably free from any concerns about a conflict of interest with the market authorisation holders of medicinal products. Committing funding for a minimum of three years would be ideal, either through a single sponsor or an agreed co-sponsorship model.

Maintenance requirements

Costs relating to the maintenance of the website will include web hosting fees, application support and updates of website functionalities in case of improvements. The maintenance of scientific content is managed as part of the regular revisions of medicines pages in local databases.

Growth plans

The growth strategy may be guided by the priorities of sponsoring organisations, to extend the content to:

- a) additional frequently used drugs in Europe
- b) additional frequently used drugs in other non-European countries nominated by the sponsor
- c) the formulary of drugs used in particular disease areas nominated by the sponsor

Language translations (including quality assurance of these) will be a significant portion of the annual budget. The language choices provided will depend upon the sponsor priorities and the funding available and the number of women that a translation might reach. It is hoped at least to cover all EU languages. Although most language translation costs relate to the medicines information content, a small budget will also be needed for web portal translation.

Given that it will take time to accumulate content across all classes of medicines and therapeutic areas, it may be possible to prioritise inclusion of medicines information that is recognised to be otherwise poorly available and to adversely affect health and pregnancy outcomes in the prenatal period.

Whilst many of the medicines that can be safely used in pregnancy, or are not safe to use in pregnancy, have been summarised by one or more TIS centres, the requirements of a sponsor may include coverage of medicines not yet reviewed and summarised by any TIS centre. In such cases, provided that funding exists for new content development, a TIS centre may be commissioned to create these pages. MUMS would only be able to establish its own content authoring capability, downstream, if the significant additional cost of new content creation is assured.

It should be noted that sponsors may influence the future priorities of medicines, disease areas, languages and countries, but will not influence the scientific process or medicine specific content.

Time plan

We are working on the three-year plan which is aimed to deliver 40 new information pages each year to reach a total of 120 drugs with an available information page in all languages at the end of year 3.

Sponsorship and budget request

Funding is required to widen the medicines content coverage, translate the lay summaries into multiple languages, to ensure the existing content remains up-to-date and clinically accurate, and for promotion. Several national TIS centres have agreed to make their medicines information content available to MUMS to repackage and reuse, at no cost, so the required funding is to assimilate, streamline and quality check this content, and to translate, host and promote the portal. This makes that the required funding is to assimilate, streamline and quality check the content, to undertake translations and to promote the resource within target countries (to be agreed with the sponsor).

Ideally MUMS should have a three-year funded plan, covering maintenance and incremental growth, costing between €200K and €250K per year.